

Assessing Children’s Pronunciation of Nordic Languages

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Abstract

We report on a number of corpora of Nordic languages spoken by children that we collected during the Teflon project. We focused on two speaker groups: non-native children learning a Nordic language (L2) and L1 children with speech sound disorder (SSD).

This abstract is a summary of the paper recently presented in Olstad et al. (2024). There, we report on the experience collecting a number of corpora aimed at creating automatic pronunciation assessment for children speaking selected Nordic languages. The goal was to develop a game to assist pronunciation training for two target groups: foreign children learning a second language (L2) and native children with speech sound disorder (SSD).

Although corpora suitable for research on child speech recognition exist for several languages (Eskenazi et al., 1997; Khaldoun et al. 1997; Pradhan and Ward, 2021; Cucchiarini and Smits, 2008; Yu et al., 2021) those do not include recordings of L2 learners or children with SSD. L2 corpora are much rarer (Zhang et al., 2021; Vidal et al., 2019; Sudhakara et al., 2019; Shi et al., 2020) and only contain limited recordings of children. Finally, there are to the authors’ knowledge no corpora that address non-standard or L2 pronunciation of Nordic languages for child speakers.

The Teflon project collected three corpora with L2 recordings of foreign children learning Norwegian, Finnish and Swedish, and two corpora with native Swedish children with SSD. We also describe some preliminary results in developing automatic pronunciation assessment in this particular domain. The full details can be found in Olstad et al. (2024).

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